

EDUCATIONAL EXPERT SYSTEMS FOR COMPUTER-AIDED
DESIGN OF CONTROL SYSTEMS

Gary B. Lamont

Department of Electrical and Computer
Engineering
School of Engineering
Air Force Institute of Technology
AFIT/ENG, WPAFB
Dayton, Ohio 45433

ABSTRACT

Expert systems for the teaching of design, must incorporate "design process models" explicitly. To study the various elements of such a process, specific expert systems have been designed to guide the control engineering student. Graphics, simulation and conventional and AI programming concepts are combined to generate a generic "design associate" on a personal computer (PC). Expert system organization for design consist of two general forms: shallow reasoning ES using empirical rules and facts; and deep reasoning employing a hierarchical model reference form (structure and function; meta-knowledge). Each hierarchical structure is treated initially as a primitive model. But if design problems exist with this primitive it is decomposed into its functional element and heuristically evaluated. This paper discusses the various developmental aspects of an educational expert system for CAD. The components of such an expert system organization including human-machine interfacing, search processing and knowledge representation selections are analyzed for application to engineering education. Formal student and faculty evaluation of prototype expert system development are encouraging and have suggested a variety of system extensions.

INTRODUCTION

Expert systems (ES), originally touted by Artificial Intelligence (AI) researchers, have gained considerable acceptance [11] in solving complex problems such as those associated with design [29]. Computer-aided design (CAD) packages were historically developed to augment and improve efficiency of the design process. Unfortunately, CAD tools usually fall short of providing a comprehensive design environment for education. An expert system can provide a user-computer interface that is more powerful, flexible, and helpful in the educational design process as well as providing contemporary design experience.

The general structure of an ES for CAD consists of a user interface, existing CAD tools, inference engine (search technique) working memory and domain knowledge (the knowledge-base) which can be considered integral elements of the design process. Domain knowledge for design includes models and a collection of analysis and synthesis approaches. The associated data dictionary and the program library provide information and procedures for inference processing. The refinement structure ("working memory") stores

the current incomplete design configuration at each stage as developed by the integrated search (inference) process. For extensive designs a database management system (DBMS) is needed for the the abundance of knowledge as well as configuration control.

This paper addresses the issues underlying the development of an educational computer-aided design (CAD) expert system for controller design and digital circuit design. The research is based on an analysis of the specific system design process. The background and historical information concerning CAD is discussed first. An overview of the generic issues, problem decomposition, design characteristics, and specific AI techniques to implement an expert system are presented with emphasis on the development of TOTAL-EASE [24], an expert system for control engineering and on a digital integrated circuit design associate [37]. Evaluation of the system is accomplished using a series of test problems and a questionnaire process.

BACKGROUND

A student often employs heuristics or "rules of thumb" in design, but they rarely result in a final acceptable solution without interactive feedback and analysis. CAD tools typically provide most of the manipulative functions required to synthesize and analyze a design based on objects and requirements, but contain very little knowledge of the design "process" itself. In essence, the student manually defines objects (entities) whose attributes are to be instantiated (given values) in an iterative manner. For example, the development of a second-order compensator (object) requires the instantiation of its coefficients (attributes) based upon desired performance requirements (over-shoot, damping, ...). The computer-aided control system design (CACSD) package provides input/output dialogue for the coefficients (or poles and zeros) as well as manipulating these attributes to determine performance.

In the design of digital integrated circuits such objectives as minimizing the number of gates, gate inputs and interconnections and propagation delay are difficult to achieve collectively in part due to packaging constraints. Various CAD tools permit the student to select appropriate ICs, but the design implementation and testing (simulation) are under the explicit direction of the engineering student.

Higher level conceptual design steps such as determining how previous design experience

relates to the present problem, determining the appropriateness of a "design model(schema)" or "design procedure" to the present problem, and determining the effects of unmodeled characteristics could be supported by ES.

CAD software is a tool, and as such, the student must direct the process and interpret its output. For example, the flowchart in Figure 1 reflects a classical and manual design approach for single-input single-output (SISO) compensator development using root-locus analysis. The efficiency of such a design process depends on design experience and expertise in using an associated CAD tool. The development of an associated ES would provide inexperienced, as well as experienced students considerable benefit.

In developing an ES for design, the initial emphasis is on a prototype to demonstrate technical feasibility. Specific objectives include identifying experts, problem understanding, selection of knowledge representatives, selecting an implementation language or ES tool, initial development and testing. Once the prototype is proven to be feasible, then a full scale development can proceed.

GENERIC ISSUES IN DESIGN PROCESS AUTOMATION

Design

Design is a very complex and not a completely understood process partially because it is abstract and requires creativity. An expert system for CAD must explicitly model the "design process" and the "design knowledge", sometimes called intelligence (fact, rules, processes), embodied in the expert designer. This implies that a method of extracting, manipulating, and applying knowledge throughout the design must also be incorporated. Although this is a complex task, a simple model of the high-level design process [28] consists of:

1. Given a set of performance requirements, selection of a set of conceptual objects with appropriate attributes (for a control application, this may consist of a plant model, specific attribute values such as overshoot and settling time, processing time constraints, ...).

2. Extraction of "important" information from experts as well as current and previous designs and techniques discussed in contemporary publications (for example in control engineering, an initial representative selection might include references [3,9,10,12,21,23]). For discrete circuit design references [13, 18] might be consulted.

3. Storing and manipulating the "important" information from #2 and design experience (from #4 if desired) through the knowledge-base

[(Object, Attribute, Value) structures], inference engine (search) and associated CAD tools using interactive feedback to determine specific values of the attributes that meet performance requirements.

4. Applying previous design knowledge to the

current problem using pattern matching search techniques through the use of schemata. This technique is known as case-based reasoning or reasoning by analogy. This method is very difficult to implement because of the type of data available and its incompleteness.

The engineering student usually accomplishes these steps external to the CAD tool. Consequently, this process is prone to error and inconsistencies, due in part, to the students capabilities and the fact that each decision and design step are not completely understood and usually not documented.

Underlying the simplicity of this model is a myriad of complex decisions which are made based on experience and the completeness of the design process itself. Partial synthesis algorithms maybe supported within CAD tools. Design tasks such as assessing the validity of the synthesis procedure are often left to the student. Furthermore, assumptions used in the design must be tracked to ensure that they are not violated. Some of the relatively simple tasks are often incorrectly executed or violated, invalidating further steps. Many of these design errors can be avoided by explicitly representing more of the design process [20]. To improve the design model, intermediate design steps, design assumptions, design commitments, and decision making must be explicitly represented. Several approaches are:

- * Definition and representation of an idealized design history
- * Defining the various design goals as a graph/tree
- * Providing an explanation capability.
- * Integration of heuristic and algorithmic knowledge
- * Development of an extensive user interface
- * Use of rule-based and model reference systems

Process Modeling

Since design is an iterative feedback process, a major attribute of an intelligent CAD tool is the ability to modify its approach based on previous design iterations. Search is one way the system can systematically try different approaches. However, search, by itself, doesn't necessarily imply intelligent behavior. It must be guided in a manner that interacts intelligently with the user and that models how the expert solves the problem. This can be accomplished by formally representing the problem as a production system (a rule based expert system) or a model-reference system. The rules or heuristics limit and direct the search process for an acceptable design. Describing the problem in this manner facilitates the search process and reflects a less complex model for "intelligent" behavior [25]. Other methods of knowledge structures such as frames, semantics nets and predicate logic for more detailed information representations may also be appropriate. A shallow reasoning ES then uses a set of finite rules and facts of which relatively few are used to determine and evaluate the results of a design decision (a rule-based system). The model reference techniques uses a hierarchical form of deep reasoning based upon structural decomposition.

Hierarchical Design Activity Modeling

Recently, diagnostic expert systems have incorporated a hierarchical modeling representation based on structure and function. The intent of this discussion is to discuss the possibility of incorporating the model representation into the design process. If the current design parameter or parameters do not generate the desired performance specifications within a priori given bounds (i.e., unacceptable behavior), then the current design state is iterated. The unacceptable behavior is also known as a "violated expectation [8] since the original design decision attempted to generate the desired performance. The associated design activity then is a feedback operation based upon diagnosing the inadequacy of the current design state (incomplete). If the design process history up to the current state is available in some type of knowledge base (rules/fact: hierarchical structure) and the general design process is known for the specific domain, then a model-based expert system is possible. Of course, the computer languages and DBMS used to implement the storage of associated history and reflect the design process should be selected based upon efficiency (machine and user) and effectiveness. The specific criteria would depend upon the user's environment.

The model-reference technique relies on reasoning from an unacceptable-behavior situation to determining where the design problem is located in a hierarchical structure. That is, it is desired to determine the detailed design decision in the hierarchical structure that generated the unacceptable performance, modify the decision or decisions, move backup the hierarchy and continue the design feedback process forward.

Figure 1.

The use of the model reference in the "design associate" is a form of deep reasoning. Deep reasoning uses the methods of first principles, causal reasoning and reasoning from the principle of locality. Reasoning from first principles reflects the ability to design based upon physical laws and observation. Casual reasoning uses the knowledge of relationships (mechanisms, paths) between design decisions to understand their mutual effects. The principle of locality focus on design decisions that related in the same manner. Using these conceptual methods in the decomposing (tree research) of the hierarchical design decisions can provide an efficient and effective integrated approach for a CAD expert system development.

Structural Description: In the circuit diagnostic approach [8], the interest focuses on the structural, functional and physical organizations. Using the model reference method for the control engineering design process, the emphasis is only on the structural and functional hierarchy. For example, a specific design process for lead-compensator design (control engineering) is depicted in figure 1. However, a hierarchical design process structure exists on top of this general flow diagram as shown in Figure 2. Figure 1 depicts a more specific decomposition of Figure 2 as indicated in the process list of Figure 1. The more detailed functions (modules) can be represented by rules as shown in Figure 3. Note the object-oriented structure at the higher levels, that is for this example domain, the parameters include figures of merit, operating points, frequency plots, phase angle, gain/phase margin and gain. At the highest level the reason should be from the functional module to the structural level and so forth. Once an unacceptable behavior is determined at a structural level within this tree formulation, that structural level is decomposed into functional relationships to determine the specific function (design decision) that caused the undesired behavior. If an explicit

Figure 2.

Figure 3.

design decision was not made at that structural design-process level, then the specific function is further decomposed (structural levels) until an incorrect design decision is found.

Functional Description: The functional description language normally uses the standard knowledge-base representation types; i.e., frames, scripts, rules,... The functional description is a behavior description that relates input to output at a particular structural level (view). Also, constraint relationships (limits) are included usually as rules. For example, see Figure 3. These forms then permit the use of inferences about the current state of the design parameters at a particular level. The manipulator then retains historical information relating to the decision dependency information or "how" the current design state was obtained. That is, what design process used the decision, interrelated decisions and the associated parameter values at that level.

The manipulator can execute the model reference part of the ES at a variety of hierarchical levels; i.e., a multi-level simulation of the system and the associated design process. The specific level at the current time is on a search path from higher level to a lower level attempting to find the critical decision(s) that caused the design to be out of specification.

The model-reference ES can help determine the problem by executing the structural model of input-output relationships or by decomposing the current level object-oriented model into a functional model and determining the function (decision) that caused the problem. A interactive capability is also

suggested in order to permit user define semantics (understanding) to direct the details of the design process as appropriate. This approach lends itself to object-oriented program development. That is, there is message flow from one structural component to another.

Manipulator (Search) Process: As shown in Figure 2, one view of the design process can be thought of as a decision tree which can require extensive and exhaustive consideration of possible designs. In the particular approach indicated the focus is on determining the decision point within a selected general design approach that caused the unacceptable behavior. It is assumed that an explicit set of design faults along with their associated corrections is not available. This information would have to be generated based upon analogy with previous designs and each one checked in sequence until the problem source was determined. Therefore, the violated expectation approach is employed instead to determine mismatches between expected parameter values and those obtained from specific design decisions.

The advantage of this approach is that it is essentially a feedback diagnostic approach which lends itself very nicely to expert system organization. The method tends to focus on the solution efficiently since a depth-first formulation is suggested (not guaranteed). However, there exists some subtleties that can occur. For example, the selected design process may include some hidden or implicit assumptions that promote a breath-first approach.

Other Considerations

In the development of TOTAL-EASE, the CAD tool employed is ICECAP-PC which is a personal computer version of ICECAP (Interactive Control Engineering Computer Analysis Package) written in Pascal. This development is based upon a continuing series of research efforts [2,13,14,15,22] with the object of providing a well documented package for continuous and discrete control system synthesis and analysis. Both classical and modern techniques are represented along with an extensive menu driven (functional language) interface.

Another consideration associated with the expert system development is the extent to which the design process can be automated. The program must be cognizant of and flexible enough to meet the user's desires and approaches to solving the problem. TOTAL-EASE for example suggests certain design algorithms (approaches) with associated parameters. As specific approaches are selected, current design results (partial solutions) are evaluated in an interactive mode using a depth-first search and forward chaining. The user can request a variety of on-line evaluation dialogue levels to enhance understanding of the expert system design process. Movement from one design aspect to another (the design process) is determined based upon time and frequency analysis, root-locus data and control engineering experience stored in the knowledge-base as schemata.

Although sometimes slighted, the user-machine inter-face design is probably one of the most important aspects of CAD beyond the desire to have accurate computational facilities. With contemporary technology, the "natural" language interface associated with control engineering for example could use icons, phrases and graphics to display the current state of the design as well as the provide efficient input dialogue capabilities. Current CAD packages could expand their current capability at this interface. Both ESs use some aspects of contemporary terminals by providing graphics, color high-lighting, and windowing.

PROBLEM AND DESIGN CHARACTERISTICS

Problem characteristics and domain knowledge constrain and bound the tools that can be applied to any problem. Although Rich's problem characteristics [23] may not represent a complete set, proper use eliminates the vast majority of possible search techniques and knowledge representation structures. Tradeoffs between the remaining structures can be accomplished and the appropriate structures identified for the design problem of interest.

Major characteristics of control system design include; the problem is decomposable, solution steps can be ignored (means-ends analysis), design performance is not predictable, locally optimum solutions are obtained, some knowledge is inconsistent, role of the knowledge is to represent the problem, and the problem requires human interpretation. Most design problems, in general, exhibit these characteristics. Furthermore, control system design problems are partially commutative and monotonic which means that it is not necessary to backtrack to previous states when an incorrect design path is chosen, but to jump to another path (another design approach) that may event-usually provide an acceptable controller design.

A difficult knowledge representation task is to represent dynamic knowledge which changes according to one or more design variables. An example is that which is contained in a root locus plot. Knowledge of how system characteristics such as stability, pole "dominance", system damping, speed of response, etc. change with gain are obtained from a root locus plot. Exact numbers are needed by the computer to represent the plot but the engineering student views the plot as a whole. The important knowledge appears to lie in the comparative relationships among the the design variables and general trends [25]. Thus an expert system CAD package must provide the ability to consider a multitude of relations, some explicit and some implicit, in order to generate an acceptable solution. The hierarchial model of structures and functions supports the associated identification.

SELECTION OF THE DESIGN APPROACH

Typical problems are abstractly defined using a search data structure such as a state space tree or an AND/OR graph [23,31] where each node represents a partial solution state. If a problem can be represented in such a data structure, various search strategies can be used to find a solution path through the

problem's defined search space. Expert systems use an expert's knowledge to limit the space that must be searched so that a solution, if it exists, is reached faster (efficient and effective). For the most part, the design problem is decomposable. It can be decomposed into smaller more easily solved subproblems reducing the overall complexity. This results in a problem reduction representation and leads to an AND/OR graph in which each node in the graph consists of a problem (OR types) or subproblem (AND types) that must be solved [6] and relates directly to the hierarchical model.

In the general development of an expert CAD system for control various rule structures must be explicitly stated in terms of possible rule preconditions, premises and subgoal objectives. The resulting subgoal must be checked for adherence to associate specifications and analysis of possible side-effects.

The initial state of a control system design task is "a physical system requires a control system to coerce it to operate in a particular manner." The goal state of this design system is a representation of physical device or software package which defines a controller for the particular physical system. Some subgoals may include establishing a math model of a physical system, prototyping a control system which meets desired figures of merit, implementation of the control system, etc. A representative AND/OR graph for SISO control system design techniques is shown in Figure 2. Figure 2 reflects a top-down hierarchical approach which emphasizes the strong data-driven nature of control system design and other design disciplines. Prerequisites are shown as AND branches. Considerable knowledge of the particular design problem may be required to determine whether certain prerequisites can be met. This knowledge can be implied by previous-user data, input directly by the user, or obtained from an appropriate design procedure. Finally, the structure of Figure 2 reduces the problem into manageable subproblems substructures and ensures conveniently modular expert system software. It is also straight forward to incorporate new design approaches since it involves adding new nodes to the existing AND/OR graph and thus, a complete software redevelopment is not required. Note that the flow through Figure 2 generally characterizes the flow of decision or "process" design.

Knowledge Representations

An appropriate knowledge representation structure for control design can be ascertained by answering the following questions: "How can individual objects and associated attributes be represented?", "How can the representations of individual objects be combined to form a representation of a complete problem space?", and "How can the sequences of problem states that arise in a search process be represented efficiently?" [25].

Design knowledge is generally very diverse and consists of storing facts and numbers, keeping track of previous design iteration data, executing design procedures, etc. Many control system design techniques are

proceduralized. Hidden within these procedures are various heuristics or "rules of thumb" which the designer uses to establish the solution path. For instance, a typical heuristic in classical lead compensation is to move the poles of the compensator to the left as far as possible. This will create a more "ideal" lead compensator and thus improve the transient response of the system. Considerable knowledge can also be extracted by proper interpretation of CAD outputs such as root locus and time-history plots. Knowledge representation must support these different types of knowledge, their transformation and their different methods of analysis and evaluation.

The diversity of knowledge required in design eliminates a strictly rule-based system. Rules are appropriate data structures for higher-level knowledge that is more symbolically oriented. A more generic data structure is needed to store standard data such as pole and zero locations, desired specifications, actual specifications, etc. Recent research on expert systems for control engineering indicates that a combination of knowledge representation schemes is advantageous [1,4,28,30,31,32], such as frames, and production rules for example [1]. Decision tables could also be used.

Frames are a good general purpose data structure and are conceptually relationally oriented. Also, any design process is to a great extent a script which describes typical steps in the design process. Since a script is a special version of a frame, the combination of frame and rule data structures appears to meet the needs of the design expert system. Note that a frame is an object with many attributes. The attributes may have values or calls to procedures to determine a value. AND/OR branches are represented explicitly as slots in the current frame. Knowledge needed by the next frame or the current frames "procedure" is represented in an "Actions" slot. Data stored in this slot might be LISP functions, Ada packages, C subprograms, CAD function calls, user prompts, etc.

In addition, there must be a script which describes how to derive the knowledge or data needed or required by a particular frame. The initialize procedure, management-rules, test, and end-procedure slots define a script to accomplish a procedure. The following control strategy describes how the knowledge in these slots is used:

- * Initialize the process: Initialize-procedure slot.
- * Execute the process: Procedure slot.
- * Test for convergence of the process: Test slot.
- * Update the system facts: Management-rules slot.
- * Final processing: End-procedure slot.

Of course, not all frames would need such a script, which implies that there should be two types of frames namely "procedural" and "hypothesis" frames. Hypothesis frames don't

contain any proceduralized knowledge or a script and would be used to deduce which approach or frame below it in the hierarchical structure is appropriate under the current circumstances. Procedure frames, on the other hand, contain a script containing specific instructions to accomplish what is needed. Figure 4 describes a "procedure" frame as indicated by the "procedure" value in the type slot. Hypothesis and procedure frames may have the same goal or represent OR nodes in Figure 2.

For clarity and consistency, another frame type, "prerequisite" is also necessary. This frame type eliminates ambiguities between the hypothesis/procedure frames and the prerequisite frames. Prerequisite frames must be instantiated prior to invoking the proposed hypothesis/procedure frame, consequently their ultimate goal is different. However, a prerequisite frame can contain a script similar to the procedure frame since it has already been identified as a prerequisite frame. Other fundamental knowledge or design data can easily be stored in a "data" frame. This global frame should be available to all frames listed in Figure 2.

Search Technique

There are several observations that may indicate which search strategy is appropriate. These observations are as follows:

- A clear cut design approach may not exist
- Design is an iterative feedback process
- Each design approach only applies to certain system types.
- There may be many different design approaches available.

An appropriate search strategy must support extensive user interaction because of the iterative nature of design. It must also explain its answers and approaches in a manner that the student understands [7]. Finally, the engineering student is usually not concerned with finding the "optimal" solution, just one that meets specifications since optimal is difficult to define. Thus, types of "depth-first" or "generate and test" search processes can be employed in traversing the AND/OR search graph (tree).

Based on these requirements, the design process doesn't appear to fall into any one search technique category. It is virtually impossible to accurately predict a control system's performance before it is developed because modeling and design approximations are used. A comprehensive system design may include solutions using several different design approaches such that performance tradeoffs on these different designs can be achieved.

A reasonable search strategy is to choose a possible solution path, based on the plant characteristics and the designer's preference, and generate the solution for that path. If the solution does not meet the desired objectives (figures of merit in control system design for example) the designed system may be modified through the hierarchical model

(structure/function) flow. A new design approach is attempted, based on the previous iterative solutions and general design "rules of thumb". These types of searches can be considered recursive and goal-oriented.

As is mentioned earlier, the problem reduction technique using the hierarchical model is appropriate for the control system design problem. A simple depth-first search, in combination with the problem reduction imposed by Figure 2, defines a reasonable search strategy. These two search strategies in combination define a generate-and-test search strategy with backtracking. The search is heuristically guided by employing an appropriate backtracking strategy.

TOTAL-EASE VALIDATION

A very desirable feature of any computer program is that it function according to its requirements. Since TOTAL-EASE is based on expert system philosophies and structures, it is difficult to develop specific tests which can demonstrate robustness and completeness. The term robust refers to the breadth of problems which TOTAL-EASE can correctly solve. TOTAL-EASE is only as robust and complete as the knowledge contained in its rules and the flexibility in its representation of the control system design process. Consequently, TOTAL-EASE was tested as a system as opposed to testing specific components or subroutines.

Several problems from reference [21:Chapter 10] were chosen as a basis for testing TOTAL-EASE.

It is important to remember that for certain pole/ zero placement strategies, the student can position the compensator poles and zeros arbitrarily. Therefore, not all of the results are equivalent but show "close" correlation in the approach and critical data. All TOTAL-EASE solutions were generated using its expert system. The figures of merit for the TOTAL-EASE solutions were obtained by using ICECAP and the TOTAL-EASE generated lead compensators. Initial compensators don't always yield desired results. Each new iteration demonstrates an approach that a beginning controls student could employ if iterations are necessary. This approach provides a student with a better understanding of the iterative nature of control system design.

The six problems presented exemplify the types of beginning control system design problems TOTAL-EASE can solve. Since this investigation was developed for the novice control engineer, this breadth of test problems is considered to be appropriate. There will always be some variability in any solution because the user can choose many different zero locations for the arbitrary pole placement methods.

TOTAL-EASE EVALUATION

A measure of the program's user friendliness or user satisfaction must be established. A method to statistically measure user satisfaction was defined through user responses to a questionnaire [28]. Questionnaires normally consisted of numerous questions relating to a number of factors such as accuracy, content, reliability, etc.

Before user satisfaction can be measured it must be defined. Bailey and Pearson [5] define it as "the sum of one's feelings or attitudes toward a variety of factors affecting the situation."

TOTAL-EASE's user interface was evaluated by using the tool previously described. In addition to a limited number of students, faculty at AFIT and engineers at the Air Force Flight Dynamics Laboratory assisted in the evaluation. While this evaluation may not be statistical relevant or comprehensive the results obtained can be used to guide future efforts. These results indicate positive user satisfaction.

CONCLUSIONS

Any expert system development requires an in-depth look at the structure and content of the knowledge being modeled. For a CAD expert system, this includes explicitly defining the control system design process and its associated detailed design in particular, in a proceduralized manner acquired through literature and experience. Design knowledge establishes which steps in the design process should be attempted and ignored thus yielding a design solution.

Design is a very difficult and complex task containing multiple subtasks. The way to address design is to explicitly represent the hierarchical design process model and its knowledge. The integration of a production rule-based systems and hierarchical model reference structure is a better emulation of designer behavior than either approach alone. User-formalized TOTAL-EASE evaluation indicates that the expert system is currently a good tutor. While the basic design process was defined, additional effort is required to develop a robust lead/lag, PID and feedback compensation capability in TOTAL-EASE with complete simulation facilities.

Various ES for control engineering have been developed [4,7,28,29,30,31,32] for constrained domains. Results indicate limited ES success with additional efforts required to generate more robust design associates. In this vein, standardization [15] of interfaces at some level would permit interchange of designs, modules and user machine interfaces and provide for more efficient and effective development of ES for general control engineering applications.

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